

MANAGEMENT OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotasiya

Maqolada marketing faoliyati va uning tashkil etish tamoyillari, mutaxassislarga bo'lgan talab va taklifni o'rganish usullari, mutaxassislar bozorini tashkil etish shart-sharoitlari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar yoritilgan.

Annotation

The article covers marketing activities and the principles of its organization, methods of studying the demand and supply of specialists, and information on the conditions for the organization of the specialist market.

There are many definitions of marketing. In a general sense, Marketing (visual marketing - sales, market trade) means the management of the creation of goods and services and their sale as a single set of processes.

Philip Kotlyar, a world-renowned expert in the field of marketing, gives the following definition: "Marketing is a type of human activity aimed at satisfying the needs and wants through exchange."

According to Peter Drucker, another expert in the field of modern management: "The purpose of marketing is to eliminate confusion about supply. Its purpose is to understand and understand the customer so well that the product or service is absolutely suitable for the customer and makes the sale for him.

There are more than 1000 definitions of marketing on earth. In this manual, it was found acceptable to use the following wording of the definition: "Educational services marketing is a management process that includes predicting and satisfying the needs of consumers and ensuring the sustainable development of an educational institution. envisages development in such a way as to achieve profit".

This definition makes it possible to understand what processes marketing includes and what goals it pursues. It is better to start studying the essence of marketing of educational services from its constituent elements: subjects and objects of educational services. Subjects of marketing of educational services, as a rule, include: educational institutions, consumers of services, organizations

and structures that carry out the activities of promoting educational services in the market. In the case we are studying, the professional educational institution (educational institution) itself is considered as an educational institution, and its consumers can be both legal entities and natural persons. In addition, it can be said that the final consumers (object) of the marketing of the educational institution's services are mostly representatives of the older population. For this reason, adults, as the final consumers, have a significant influence on the choice of education sources, forms, place, and time. Marketing relations for the provision of educational services, its programs and other types of services are formed around the interests of adults who act as consumers of educational courses.

From the point of view of practical marketing, the following can be included among the main tasks of educational services marketing performed by an educational institution:

In order to have a clearer idea of the uniqueness of educational services, it is necessary to consider the special and important aspects of teaching as a type of service. For example, let's take a look at some of the main specific aspects of the activity of an educational institution that must be taken into account when organizing a marketing service.

First: Educational services are non-emotional, that is, they cannot be seen, heard, felt, and evaluated until they have purchased and started using them.

Second: The processes of presentation and consumption cannot be separated from each other. It is consumed after the purchase of other goods, but it is

consumed at the same time that the educational service is provided. The main distinguishing feature of the educational service is that in the process of providing it, a close relationship is formed between the service provider and the consumer.

Third: Educational courses and programs as a type of service are characterized by their instability and unsatisfactory quality, and its main indicators depend on many factors and content creators. For example, the quality of teaching in one educational course depends on the content and methodology, the level of training of the teacher conducting the course, the composition and enthusiasm of the audience, even the lesson schedule and the season of the year. may be different.

It is also necessary to take into account that the range of evaluation of its quality indicator is extremely private when receiving educational services. Evaluation of the quality of the educational course is closely related to how a particular person accepts this or that educational methodology, the knowledge and skills that this person already has, and the requirements and wishes he places on the content of the educational program. It can be seen that all of the above may be different for different people studying in the same course. This results in different grades given by the students of the same course.

Fourth: Educational services differ by their nature, for example, they are not reserved for those who do not show up on time or miss a session. While it is possible to use other people's notes or training handouts, there is no way to repeat a missed session or repeat the same content. It is also worth noting that acquired knowledge can be forgotten, lost, and outdated, which creates the need to constantly update and supplement it.

In conclusion, it can be said that educational service is offered by one party (educational institution) to the other party (audience) in order to achieve quantitative and qualitative changes in the level of knowledge, skills, professional and personal qualifications, through emotions. an incomprehensible type of activity is envisaged. The provision of educational services is closely related to the provision of services to students, the quality of management of the educational process, and the chosen marketing strategy. The educational services offered by the educational institution ultimately form the attentive attitude of consumers towards it and have a direct impact on the increase in profit.

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